

Studies with Inorganic Ion-exchange Membranes. Permeation of Salt Solutions through a Parchment- supported Titanium Arsenate Membrane

S. K. SRIVASTAVA*, SATISH KUMAR**, C. K. JAIN and SURENDER KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667

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The permeation of salt solutions, viz., LiCl, NaCl, KCl, BaCl₂, CaCl₂, and MgCl₂, through parchment-supported titanium arsenate membrane has been studied at various temperatures. Permeability studies reveal the order, $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ for various cations. The thermodynamic parameters for the diffusion process have also been evaluated. These parameters alongwith permeability have been related to hydration number, heats of hydration etc.

INORGANIC ion-exchange membranes have acquired a particular significance, however, they have made little headway as models for biological membranes in spite of the fact that comparatively simple systems can be envisaged and subsequently synthesised. In continuation of our earlier work on such membranes¹⁻³, we report herein the selective permeation of some salt solutions through a parchment-supported titanium arsenate membrane. The thermodynamic parameters for the process have been evaluated and their relationship with various thermodynamic quantities of the aqueous ions have also been considered.

Experimental

Preparation of membrane: The membrane was prepared by impregnating parchment paper with titanium arsenate. The paper was first soaked in distilled water and then tied carefully to an open glass cylinder. A 0.05 M titanous chloride solution was filled inside the paper container which was then suspended in a beaker containing 0.05 M sodium arsenate solution for 24 h. It was then taken out and washed repeatedly with distilled water to remove the adsorbed electrolytes. Titanous chloride and sodium arsenate solutions were then interchanged and the paper was immersed in these solutions for another 24 h. The white membrane thus obtained was repeatedly washed with double-distilled water for complete removal of the adsorbed electrolytes.

Permeability measurement: The constant flow methods recommended by Willis⁴, was used. All experiments were performed with 0.05 M metal chloride solutions and the flow rate of water as well as the solution was maintained at 50 ml h⁻¹. For evaluating the thermodynamic parameters, permeability of salt solutions was determined at four temperatures, viz. 20, 25, 30 and 35°.

Results and Discussion

The permeability values of various salt solutions and the thermodynamic parameters as computed from the permeability data at different temperatures, are given in Tables 1 and 2. Various factors which control the electrolyte permeability through a membrane are the charge on the membrane, its porosity, the charge and size of the diffusing ion.

The process of permeation would involve the entry of cations into the membrane phase by ion-exchange followed by diffusion to the other side of the membrane. Obviously, the ionic size, hydration and association are some of the important factors which would affect the process. The permeability sequence, $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ \sim \text{NH}_4^+$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ obtained with this membrane is in accordance with their ionic size.

The permeation selectivity, according to Eisenman¹⁰, depends on the energies of hydration and ion-site interaction. For ion-exchangers with fixed charged groupings having weak field strength, the selectivity sequence is governed by differences in hydration energies of counter ions. In such cases, a normal sequence, e.g. $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{Rb}^+ < \text{Cs}^+$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ is followed. On the other hand, for ion-exchangers with charged groupings having high field strength, the selectivity sequence is governed by crystallographic radii of counter ions. In such cases, a reverse selectivity sequence, e.g. $\text{Li}^+ > \text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Rb}^+ > \text{Cs}^+$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+} > \text{Ba}^{2+}$ should result. For ion-exchangers having charged grouping of intermediate field strength, Eisenman¹⁰ and Sherry¹¹ predicted a number of intermediate selectivity sequences. As such, the sequence, $\text{Li}^+ < \text{Na}^+ < \text{K}^+ = \text{NH}_4^+$ and $\text{Mg}^{2+} < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+}$ observed in the present case, points towards a weak field strength of charged groupings. These findings are in full agreement with the data on membrane charge density which

*Institute of Paper Technology, Saharanpur (University of Roorkee).

TABLE 1—PERMEABILITY OF UNIVALENT AND DIVALENT METAL CHLORIDES THROUGH A TITANIUM ARSENATE MEMBRANE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	Permeability (mol h ⁻¹)						
	LiCl	NaCl	KCl	NH ₄ Cl	MgCl ₂	CaCl ₂	BaCl ₂
20	1.99	5.84	5.21	9.61	0.520	0.785	1.58
25	2.95	6.32	7.65	10.80	0.737	0.895	2.32
30	4.31	7.67	9.62	10.40	0.794	0.927	2.51
35	5.00	9.60	11.02	12.58	0.824	0.964	3.08

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION ENERGY AND OTHER THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTROLYTE DIFFUSION THROUGH A TITANIUM ARSENATE MEMBRANE

Electrolyte	E _a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔF [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
LiCl	45.94	43.46	45.81	-7.88
KCl	36.15	33.67	43.42	-32.71
NaCl	28.91	26.43	43.89	-53.59
NH ₄ Cl	22.59	20.12	42.55	-75.26
BaCl ₂	30.63	28.15	49.03	-70.06
CaCl ₂	16.65	14.17	46.40	-108.15
MgCl ₂	16.40	13.92	49.24	-118.52

are quite low (with KCl at concentration 1.0 M, $\bar{x}=0.085$, and at 0.05 M, $\bar{x}=0.075$). For other gels like stannic molybdate, zirconium phosphate etc. the respective values of \bar{x} with KCl at the same concentrations are between 0.25 and 0.59.

The hydration number (*n*) for the individual ions are plotted against permeability in Fig. 1. The number *n* as given by Stokes and Robinson¹², in

Fig. 1. Plots of permeability vs hydration number (*n*).

general, reflects the average effect of all ion-solvent interactions and does not necessarily represent the number of water molecules around the ion, in their first layer. The curve (Fig. 1) shows that lower the values of hydration number, higher is the permeability. Noyes¹³ while investigating the thermodynamics of ion hydration, observed that the effective dielectric properties of solvents (ϵ_{eff}) are a function of ionic size, primarily, and adsorbability, which is related to polarisability, also affects diffusion and

reduces the effective hydration¹⁴. As such the effective dielectric constant, (ϵ_{eff}), Z/a^2 (where *a* is the mean distance of approach as defined by Stokes and Robinson¹²) and various other thermodynamic parameters of ion hydration are correlated to permeability of cations across the titanium arsenate membrane in Figs. 2-4.

The values of ΔF^{\ddagger} have been calculated by absolute reaction rate theory for the process of diffusion¹⁵ using the equation (1),

$$P' = \left(\frac{\lambda^2 kT}{dh}\right) e^{-\Delta F^{\ddagger}/RT} \quad (1)$$

where, *P'* is permeability (cm s⁻¹), *k* the Boltzmann constant, *d* the membrane thickness and λ is the average distance between two successive positions during the process of diffusion. The value of λ has

Fig. 2. Plots of permeability vs (1) ϵ_{eff} and (2) Z/a^2 .

Fig. 3. Plots of permeability vs (1) ΔF°_{con} (conventional free energy change), (2) ΔF°_{el} (electrostatic free energy) and (3) ΔH°_{el} (electrostatic enthalpy change of hydration).

Fig. 4. Plots of permeability vs (1) ΔS°_{con} (conventional entropy change) and (2) ΔS°_{el} (electrostatic entropy change of hydration).

been taken as 3×10^{-8} cm on the basis of investigations reported by Lai and Mortland¹⁶. It is observed that the permeability increases with temperature. The slope of $\log P$ vs $1/T$ plots (not shown here) gives the activation energy E_a for the process of diffusion. Thus the enthalpy of activation ΔH° as well as entropy of activation ΔS° have been evaluated from the equations (2) and (3),

$$\Delta H^{\circ} = E_a - RT \quad (2)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta F^{\circ} = \Delta H^{\circ} - T\Delta S^{\circ} \quad (3)$$

The values of ΔF° , ΔH° and ΔS° thus obtained are given in Table 2. It is observed that the entropy of activation ΔS° is negative for all the cations investigated in this work. In general, these values are higher than those reported for silver chloride and other inorganic membranes¹⁷. According to Zwolniski¹⁵, the values of ΔS° indicate the mechanism of flow and the breakage of bonds while low and negative values indicate that activation is accompanied by a decrease in entropy and this being possible only if the activated state involved the formation of a bond between the diffusing ion and the membrane material.

In the light of investigations reported by Barrer¹⁸, a high entropy of activation also suggests the existence of a large zone of activation or the reversible loosening of ordered segments of the membrane during the process of diffusion.

The efforts to correlate the thermodynamic parameters for the diffusion process across the titanium arsenate membrane, with the corresponding parameters for ion hydration, have not met with success. The free energy and enthalpy change is found to be positive for the system under investigation while the same parameters have negative values in ion hydration.

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